

Facile synthesis of a novel Ternary Hybrid Hetero junction Photocatalyst (g-C₃N₄/CuO-ZnO) for Water splitting Hydrogen production Applications.

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Abstract

The utilization of solar energy for water splitting paves a way for environmentally friendly H₂ generation. The synthesis of g-C₃N₄ and CuO-ZnO powders was achieved using a conventional pyrolysis and co-precipitation method, respectively. A novel ternary hybrid hetero-junction photocatalyst g-C₃N₄/CuO-ZnO was subsequently prepared through grinding and sonication. The structures, morphologies and optical properties of the photocatalysts were comprehensively characterized and compared with those of g-C₃N₄. X-ray diffraction results revealed that the g-C₃N₄/CuO-ZnO sample has well crystallized structure. Spectroscopic results obtained via FT-IR technique were consistent with the layered structure of sp² hybridized bonding features of C and N in g-C₃N₄ besides Cu-O, Zn-O stretching vibrations. Photoluminescence results revealed that CuO-ZnO hybridization with g-C₃N₄ showed efficient separation and delayed recombination of photoinduced electron-hole pairs. Microscopy analysis clearly displayed that CuO-ZnO nanoparticles are anchored on g-C₃N₄ and showed the interface between the CuO-ZnO and g-C₃N₄. The g-C₃N₄/CuO-ZnO nanocomposites exhibited enhanced visible light photocatalytic H₂ production.

Keywords : Ternary hybrid, heterojunction, Hydrogen production